

Impact Study Rare Diseases & Genetic Diagnostics

Rare Diseases & Genetic Diagnostics

Context

With around [8 in 10](#) rare conditions stemming from genetic mutations, genomic data and diagnostics are revolutionising our ability to provide support to patients and their families. Advances in genomic sequencing technologies, bioinformatics analysis and precision medicine approaches are enabling researchers and clinicians to more rapidly identify causative genetic variants, design targeted therapies and offer personalised care plans tailored to each patient's unique genetic profile.

This series of case studies demonstrates how biodata resources have contributed to our understanding, treatment and management of rare diseases.

Diagnosing blood disorders

The [NIHR BioResource](#) is a resource containing data from over 250,000 volunteers who have agreed to participate in health-related research, including those with and without health conditions. The NIHR supports researchers from industry and academia through the provision of clinical and/or genetic data, samples of DNA (blood/saliva), plasma or serum, as well as by supporting researchers in recalling volunteers to take part in new research (e.g. fresh samples or online questionnaires).

The NIHR BioResource played a [significant role](#) in the formal designation of DIAPH1 as a gene associated with a blood disease, according to the American College of Medical Genetic and Genomic criteria. This designation has been recognised and cited in resources that list human genetic disorders curated by [Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man \(OMIM\)](#), [ClinGen](#) and the [International Society of Thrombosis and Haemostasis](#). The NIHR BioResource contributed to this discovery by enabling the identification of patients with DIAPH1 gene changes revealing hitherto unrecognised immune system defects. Since discovery, the blood disorder caused by DIAPH1 gene changes has been reported in tens of further cases in the scientific literature or online gene mutation catalogues.

The study leads [also showed](#) that DIAPH1 gene changes can cause haematological and hearing abnormalities. Genetic testing in families with variations in the DIAPH1 gene has allowed for the early detection of infants who are at an increased risk of developing hearing loss. This timely identification enables the implementation of preventive measures to mitigate the potential for developmental delays. Furthermore, in cases where hearing loss has already occurred, early diagnosis facilitates the reversal of hearing impairment through the use of cochlear implants.

Tackling rare diseases

A [recent study](#) demonstrated that genome sequencing can be used as a first-line test to replace exome sequencing and chromosomal microarray testing, demonstrating its superior ability to detect multiple types of disease-causing variation. In particular, the researchers showed that genome sequencing was needed to detect the causal variant that was missed by exome sequencing or targeted testing in a cohort of over 740 families with suspected rare monogenic diseases. As the cost of sequencing is decreasing, significant opportunities are opening up for the diagnosis of rare genetic diseases using whole genome sequencing.

The [methodological detail](#) provided as part of this research provides a rare insight into the interconnectedness and complementarity of biodata resources:

- OMIM was used to define known disease-associated genes. Variants in OMIM genes that explained the phenotype and were classified as pathogenic/likely pathogenic were considered to provide a definitive diagnosis.
- Population allele frequencies from [gnomAD](#) were used to filter variants, with different frequency cutoffs used for recessive vs dominant inheritance models. The gnomAD structural variants database was also used for structural variant frequencies. Additionally, genetic ancestry was imputed using the random forest model from gnomAD v2.
- For analysis of mitochondrial DNA variants, “confirmed” variants in MITOMAP and those classified as pathogenic/likely pathogenic in ClinVar were identified as candidate causal variants. Variants of uncertain significance in ClinVar or with “reported” status in MITOMAP were also reviewed.

- Candidate novel disease genes identified in unsolved cases were submitted to Matchmaker Exchange to identify additional cases with variants in the same gene and similar phenotype to aid in establishing new gene-disease associations.

In another case, gnomAD enabled the [Rare Genomes Project](#) to lead the development of a new tool, the [Genetic Prevalence Estimator \(GeniE\)](#): this tool estimates the genetic prevalence of autosomal recessive diseases using gnomAD allele frequencies and makes information [more accessible](#) to the entire genomics community by removing the requirement for computational expertise. The TANGO2 Research Foundation [used the GeniE tool](#) to estimate the genetic prevalence of TANGO2-related disease, a rare genetic disorder. GeniE discovered a pathogenic variant that was more common in individuals with an admixed American genetic ancestry, including Native North American, Central American, and Hispanic ancestries. This finding was reinforced by the observations of a board member of the TANGO2 Research Foundation, who had previously noted that many of her patients with this variant were of Mexican or Mexican-American ancestry.

Based on the higher prevalence suggested by GeniE's data, the TANGO2 Research Foundation took several actions: they strengthened collaborations in Mexico to improve diagnosis of TANGO2-related disease; they conducted educational seminars with physicians in Mexico; they developed Spanish-language literature on the disease; and they used the prevalence data to secure funding to provide more services to patients along the Mexico-Texas border.

Informing national genetic counselling

The [Clinical Genome \(ClinGen\)](#) Resource gathers phenotypic and clinical data on genomic variants, establishes consensus methods for determining their clinical significance, and shares these findings with the research and medical communities. Rett syndrome is a genetic developmental disorder that typically leads to impairments in language and coordination, and to repetitive movements. Korean researchers reviewed the variation spectrum of MECP2 in Korean Rett(-like) patients and compared it with previous reports from multiple ethnic groups, building on an updated Clinical Genome Resource guideline.

As a result of the study, three novel variants were identified, and nine variants were reclassified as pathogenic variants. The study provided a useful background for genetic counselling for the Korean population, which is particularly relevant as [South Korea's 2015 Rare Disease Management Act](#) highlighted a need for greater support for rare diseases.

Conclusions

The term '[diagnostic odyssey](#)' describes the protracted path that numerous individuals with rare diseases and their loved ones must navigate to obtain a precise diagnosis – a process that spans an average of 5.6 years in the UK. This leaves patients enduring unrelenting symptoms for long periods of time, compounded in some cases by the scepticism of medical professionals along the way.

Genetic testing is emerging as a promising methodology to address rare diseases, including as its cost is continuing to decrease and more data becomes available: by enabling early detection, facilitating timely interventions and informing genetic counselling practices, biodata resources can help improve the lives of countless patients and their families.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
ClinGen	ClinGen is a National Institute of Health (NIH)-funded resource dedicated that defines the clinical relevance of genes and variants for use in precision medicine and research. ClinGen undertakes a variety of curation activities including Gene-Disease Validity and Variant Pathogenicity. ClinGen was established in 2013 and involves over 2,500 contributors from more than 68 countries.
Genome Aggregation Database (gnomAD)	The Genome Aggregation Database is a database containing aggregated and harmonised genetic data. It spans over 730,000 exome sequences and over 76,000 whole-genome sequences from unrelated individuals, from around the world. The database was launched in 2014 as the Exome Aggregation Consortium (ExAC). Primary data is available under a CC0 license.
International Society of Thrombosis and Haemostasis	<p>The International Society of Thrombosis and Haemostasis aims to advance the understanding, prevention, diagnosis and treatment of conditions related to thrombosis and haemostasis.</p> <p>The Society hosts a ‘Scientific and Standardisation Committee’ that supports a series of registries and databases related to thrombosis and haemostasis.</p>
MITOMAP	MITOMAP was launched in 1996 and is a human mitochondrial genome database. It contains information on polymorphisms and mutations in human mitochondrial DNA. The resource holds over 60,000 full-length sequences, over 80,000 control region sequences and nearly 20,000 single nucleotide variants.
NIHR BioResource	The NIHR BioResource is a resource containing data from over 250,000 volunteers who have agreed to participate in health-related research, including both those with and without health conditions. The resource supports research through the provision of volunteer data, physical samples and study volunteer recruitment, with participants being able to be selected by specific genotype or phenotype. Participants are recruited in three key cohorts: common diseases, rare diseases and healthy populations.
Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM)	OMIM is a database containing data about human genes, genetic phenotypes and genetic disorders. The database contains information on all known Mendelian disorders and more than 16,000 genes. This resource was initiated in the early 1960s, with the online version being created in 1985. The resource focuses on the relationship between genotype and phenotype.

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